

**FEATURES OF MANAGEMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES OF
THE HEALTH CARE SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AT
THE MESO-LEVEL LINE.**

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Annotation: The given article reveals innovative activities of the health system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and analyzes its features of proper operating concerning the meso-level line. It also underlines the vital necessity of penetrating innovative methods into the health system so that the medical field of our country could be considerably improved.

Key words: innovations, management, insurance, scientific research, management system of healthcare, framework

Introduction

New requirements for competitiveness for the healthcare system are reflected, first of all, in innovative activity. A huge stock of knowledge has been accumulated in Uzbekistan, scientific research is constantly being conducted, modern technologies and new medical equipment are being developed, advanced methods of treatment are being introduced in accordance with the achieved level of medical science. At the same time, the potential of the modern healthcare system does not allow to quickly adapt to changing environmental conditions. In this system, there are obvious gaps in the mechanisms for assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of functioning and development, management, insurance, financing, information, analytical, organizational and methodological support. Under these conditions, it is necessary to manage the innovation activity of the healthcare system at the mesolevel, which would eliminate the technological backwardness from world practice, allowing to achieve the main goal of the healthcare system - reducing mortality, morbidity, disability, as well

as increasing labor productivity, building human potential.[2.] Innovative backwardness of the healthcare system is observed in almost all areas - highly qualified personnel; wages that do not motivate employees; adequate management organization; the structure of medical institutions that do not meet real needs, etc. All this requires appropriate analysis and justification. Insufficient research of this problem from the standpoint of modern economics and management of innovative activities of the healthcare system, taking into account the new economic conditions, the urgent need for practice in solving the most important national economic problem of managing innovative activities of the healthcare system at the mesolevel determined the relevance of the topic of the dissertation research.[3.]

Main part

There are a significant number of developments in the domestic and foreign literature on the problem of developing a management system for healthcare institutions. However, the algorithms and methods for managing the transformations of this system are not sufficiently developed in them in the light of the new paradigm for the development of healthcare institutions. In addition, the complexity and debatability of the problem under study confirm the importance of continuing systemic research on this issue, since targeted scientific research in the field of developing the management system of healthcare institutions has not been given due attention at the stage of reforming this area.

The work of foreign researchers R.E. is devoted to the issue of innovative development. Kelly, J. Keynes, J. Clark, L.E. Mindeli, G. Mensch, J.S. Mill, R. Nelson, M.E. Porter, G. Sabato, B. Santo, M. Huchek, T. Schulz, J. Dosi, D. Lindsay, D. Stone, P. Freeman, K. Friedman, A. Hamilton, I. Schumpeter, S. Winter, K. Arrow and other authors.

Despite a fairly large number of studies on the development of innovative activities of the healthcare system, the problem of improving the management of innovative activities in the production of medical services, the production of medical and pharmaceutical products is the focus of research by modern economists and has not been fully studied. The relevance of the study of the problem of managing

innovation and innovative development of the health care system at the mesolevel at the present time, its theoretical and practical significance, its multidimensionality and insufficient degree of development determined the choice of the topic of scientific research.[4.]

The development of competitive markets in the healthcare system, based on the stimulation of innovation, is impossible without the creation of an innovation ecosystem at the mesolevel. The concept of an innovative economic system at the mesolevel can be interpreted as a system of economic relations that arise between various institutional units of the region in the process of implementing innovative activities, including methods for regulating and managing these relations. The subjects of the innovation ecosystem at the mesolevel are innovative companies, scientists, researchers, universities, and investors. The innovation ecosystem of the mesolevel is a set of certain conditions at the mesolevel that ensure the successful creation and development of innovative enterprises that carry out innovative activities. The main elements of the meso-level innovation ecosystem are: the innovation environment, entrepreneurial experience, sources of investment and interaction mechanisms that combine the elements into a single whole.

The concept of an innovative economic system of the mesolevel is much broader than the innovative environment of the mesolevel, since it includes, in addition to innovative enterprises, innovations, mechanisms for their interaction, information networks, also innovative infrastructure, criteria and indicators for assessing innovative activity at the mesolevel, the innovative potential of the region, investment mechanisms for innovative activity. , staffing and personnel potential of the region, the regulatory framework for innovative activities in the region.[5]

Innovative activity is an activity that satisfies the need for novelty goods (products, technologies, raw materials, materials, methods of organizing production and management), including the process of creating and diffusing innovations. Innovations are the result of scientific and technical activities to create products, as a result of which the needs for novelty goods (products, technologies, raw materials, materials, methods of organizing production and management) are satisfied, including

the process of creating and diffusing innovations. Depending on the object of management, one can single out the sectoral, organizational and sectoral structures of the health care system. The main goal of managing the healthcare system is to improve the health of the population through the provision of affordable and high-quality medical care. The effectiveness of innovation management of the healthcare system at the mesolevel is the achievement of a significant increase in population health indicators per unit of resources spent on innovation. The task of increasing the efficiency of the use of resources and the quality of medical care is solved within the framework of the concept of managing the innovation activity of the healthcare system at the mesolevel. The object of management within the framework of the concept at the mesolevel is not a separate medical institution or medical enterprise, but the whole complex of interconnected medical institutions involved in innovation.

To assess the effectiveness of innovation management in the healthcare system, an algorithm is proposed that includes three stages of innovation management. At the first stage, the strategic problems of the healthcare system at the mesolevel are determined, the solution of which involves fundamentally new approaches. At the second stage in the organization of innovation activity, the search and selection of adequate technologies, the regulation of innovation activity, the training of personnel in innovation, the development and use of organizational and economic mechanisms, and the socio-psychological adaptation of innovation take place. At the third stage, the evaluation of the effectiveness of innovation management is carried out by monitoring the implementation of innovations using specially designed control systems, deviations from the set goal are taken into account, and if the initial goal is not achieved, the selected innovation is corrected. [6] The result of social innovations is the development of human capital, by which the author understands the totality of human abilities and capabilities that allow him to perform certain social, labor and economic functions. Investments in the development of human capital in the healthcare system are resources that form and accumulate new knowledge in the field of medicine, information and experience in the process of training and functioning of the medical workforce, that is, the ability to work. Of all types of investments in human capital, the most important

are investments in health, since they prolong the working life of a person, and, consequently, the time of functioning of human capital. Investing in human capital in the health care system can slow down the gradual wear and tear of human capital.

The management of innovative activities of the healthcare system at the mesolevel is necessary for the sustainable innovative development of the region, stimulating innovative activities in the development of resource-saving technologies in the healthcare system, and activating the processes of equipping healthcare institutions with modern high-tech equipment. Achieving a balance of free enterprise and state regulation at the stage of commercialization of innovations in the healthcare system is ensured through the introduction of new forms and methods of work, combined with a fully responsible attitude to the needs of patients.[7.]

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that in the management of innovative activities of the healthcare system, an entrepreneurial approach is acceptable in the following areas: equality of access to quality services, protection of public health, production of medicines and high-tech medical equipment. The management of innovative activities of the healthcare system is one of the main tools for competition, multi-layered development, and the formation of a competitive environment, since in the healthcare system the state still has the function of setting a price limit for high-tech services and innovative medicines, therefore, it is possible to win the competition only through the provision of services best quality. This can be achieved through the introduction of the latest systems of organization and management in our activities, expanding the range of high-tech services, i.e. through the development of innovative activities in the healthcare system.

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